

Elemental analysis of dugong organs

I. H. A. Rahman^{a*}, W. Chua-Anusorn^b, J. Webb^b and D. J. Macey^b

^aChemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Universiti Brunei Darussalam, Brunei, Darussalam
E-mail : Ibrahim@fos.ubd.edu.bn

^bDivision of Science, Murdoch University, Perth, W.A. 6150, Australia

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Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Mn, Ni, Co, Al, P and S have been analyzed by ICP-AES. The concentrations of Fe in all dugong livers are extremely high (13000–71000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.). The levels of Zn are also high (1500–2800 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.). The level of Fe in spleen (7600 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.), heart (340 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) and kidney (1200 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) are considerably high. Cd is mostly concentrated in kidney (60 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.). Concentrations of P and S in liver, spleen, kidney and heart are considerably high.

The dugong, *Dugong dugon* (Müller) is the only herbivorous mammal species that is strictly marine. Ecologically, the dugong occupies an important position in the shallow water ecosystems along the subtropical and tropical coasts of the Indian and western Pacific Oceans. The dugong spends most of its time feeding the seagrass. It is a large mammal that weights up to 400 kg and 3 m length¹. The seagrass that constitutes the main source of nutrition to the mammal, may take in the elements from the sediment on which the seagrass is supported. The elements may be passed on to the dugong and incorporated into its body tissue. It has been reported that the concentration of some metals such as Fe, Zn, Cu, Co and Ag in the liver of adult dugongs are extremely high compared with those reported for other marine mammals².

This paper presents the results of analysis more dugong samples. Other organs of dugong are also included to verify and attempt to explain the previous finding.

Results and Discussion

Elements in dugong liver :

Three samples of dugong liver were obtained from Shark Bay and one sample from Northern Territory. The elements were determined on freeze-dried tissue of dugong liver. The results are shown in Table 1.

The level of iron in the dugong liver ranges between 16691 and 71123 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.). The range is considerable and the largest values are extremely high. The unusually high level of iron in the dugong liver tissues supports a previous study conducted by Denton *et al.*², who reported a range between 778 and 82363 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) for dugong liver tissues of North Queensland coastal water, Australia. The maximum value found for iron in the present study is

Table 1. Concentration ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) of selected elements in dugong liver

Element	SB	SB1	SB2	QNL
Fe	4709	19309	12691	71123
Zn	2836	1572	1525	1722
Cu	467	109	24	36
Al	146	na	na	na
Cd	16.1	12.6	na	20.2
Mn	4.6	na	na	na
Ni	1.4	6.9	14.5	20.5
Co	3.0	9.2	2.6	nd
Pb	0.9	6.0	nd	22.3

na = not available, nd = not detected

far greater than that for other marine mammals^{2,3}. Robertson *et al.*³ reported a range of 3600–5000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) for Weddell seal (*Leptonychotes weddelli*). In the normal human liver the concentration range is 403–1055 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.)⁴. However, the level of iron in thalassemic liver tissue was reported to be extremely high too. A value of about 37000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) has been shown in the liver of one thalassemic patient⁴. The high concentration of iron that occurred in dugong liver tissue could be a result of a diet high in iron. The dugongs are known to feed predominantly on seagrass⁵. The level of iron in seagrass is quite high⁶. Under normal conditions, the control of iron absorption includes both luminal and mucosal factors that prevent excess absorption of iron. However, when the level of iron in the diet is very high, other factors predominate, and this results in increased absorption of iron from the diet. Usually the amount of iron absorbed is in direct proportion to the amount ingested⁷. High levels of iron in pasture plants and drinking water have also been related to bovine haemosiderosis in New Zealand⁸.

The levels of zinc in all the dugong liver samples are consistently high. The concentrations of zinc occurred in the range of about 1500 to nearly 3000 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) (Table 1). The high level of zinc is also supported by the previous finding². A range of 219–4183 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) of zinc was reported by Denton *et al.*² for dugong of north Queensland coastal water. The level of zinc in the present study is also higher than that found for other sea mammals. Robertson *et al.*³ reported the level of zinc in Weddell seal (*Leptonychotes weddelli*) to be in the range 240–310 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.), while that of leopard seal (*Hydrurga leptonyx*) in the range 150–190 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.).

The high concentrations of zinc found in dugongs in the present study are unusual. Although zinc is an essential metal and is associated in a wide range of cellular activities in living tissues, it seems unlikely that such high concentrations are required to fulfil normal biological functions in dugongs. Dietary zinc levels are clearly not the main source of such high levels in liver tissue. The levels of zinc in seagrass are low and are generally comparable with those found in pasture grasses⁹. However, the intestinal absorption of zinc in the dugong may possibly be influenced by the low levels of copper in seagrasses⁶. This is due to competition between the metals for available binding sites on carrier proteins within the intestine. Alfaro and Heaton¹⁰ showed that zinc accumulates in the livers of rats fed with a low concentration of copper in their diet. It is therefore possible that the high level of zinc in dugong liver may have resulted from the low level of copper in the diet.

The variation of copper concentrations between the samples is considerable. The levels of copper range from 24 to 467 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) (Table 1). The values are also supported by the range 9.1–608 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) reported by Denton *et al.*² for dugong of north Queensland coastal water. The highest value of copper in dugong liver tissue is much higher than that found in other sea mammals³. However, the high values of copper found in dugong liver are similar to those found in sheep and cattle⁹. In most mammals, copper level tends to be highest in young individual and usually decline when the animal approaches maturity⁹. The wide range of copper concentration found in the present study (Table 1) may be related to different ages of the dugongs. Denton *et al.*² noted that the copper concentrations in the liver of dugongs decline with age, and continue to diminish throughout their life. This suggests that the older dugongs are having lower copper levels.

The concentration of aluminum is only available for one of the dugongs (SB = 146 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt. of Al) (Table 1). The level of aluminum in the present study is high. The

high level of aluminum in seagrasses with mean value of 1427 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.)⁶ may have contributed to the high value of aluminum in the dugong liver tissue.

A detectable amount of cadmium is present in the liver of dugong. The concentration of cadmium in one sample (SB2) is not available. The level of cadmium ranges from 12.6 to 20.2 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.) (Table 1). Denton *et al.*² reported the range of cadmium to be 0.5–72.0 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.). Cadmium concentration determined in the seagrasses indicates that dietary concentration is low⁶. The levels of cadmium in sediment and seagrass are low (1 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.)⁶. Cadmium may be absorbed by seagrass and accumulate over time in the liver of dugong that feeds on seagrass¹¹.

Other metals present at low levels in the liver tissue of dugong are manganese, nickel, cobalt and lead.

Elements in spleen, kidney and heart of dugong :

The spleen, kidney and heart of one dugong from Shark Bay were available for elemental analysis. The organs came with the liver of dugong from Shark Bay referred to SB. Triplicate determinations were carried out for each sample. The mean of each element and standard deviation are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Concentration of selected elements in spleen, kidney and heart ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.)*

Element	Spleen	Heart	Kidney
Fe	7630 (331)	338 (2.0)	1226 (30)
Zn	82 (2.0)	89 (1.0)	131 (2.0)
Cu	66 (1.1)	9.3 (0.3)	10.4 (0.2)
Al	82 (14)	22.9 (3.6)	26.0 (0.4)
Cd	nd	nd	57.6 (1.0)
Mn	2.6 (0.2)	1.3 (0)	3.1 (0.1)
Ni	1.3 (1.0)	0.1 (0.5)	nd
Co	nd	nd	1.7 (0.6)
Pb	8.5 (4.3)	1.1 (0.7)	16.0 (2.2)

Standard deviation in parenthesis. nd = not detected.

The concentration of iron in spleen (7630 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) is high. This is not unexpected as the level of iron in the liver of dugong is remarkably elevated (Table 1). Iron is also known to be deposited in spleen. The spleen is an important site of phagocytosis of circulating red blood cells in

normal subjects¹². Iron from the red cell remains in the spleen and is stored as ferritin or haemosiderin.

The level of zinc and aluminum in spleen are considerable but lower than that found in the liver. The spleen also contains detectable amount of copper, manganese, nickel and lead. Other metals, such as cadmium and cobalt, were not detected in the present study.

Concentrations of iron, zinc and copper in kidney are considerably lower than in the liver tissue, while cadmium level is the highest amongst all the organs analyzed (Tables 1 and 2). The level of iron in kidney ($1226 \pm 30 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) is well within the range ($222\text{--}3059 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) reported by Denton *et al.*². The other metals in the kidney of dugong in the present study also lie within the range of the values for the kidney of dugong from a baseline study of north Queensland coastal waters².

Cadmium seems to be concentrated in the kidney. The high cadmium levels in kidney also occurred in other sea mammals such as pilot whale ($498 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) from north Queensland coastal waters, Australia². The results show that in dugong, as in most mammals⁹, cadmium is predominantly concentrated in kidney and liver tissues (Tables 1 and 2). Comparatively, cadmium is not detected in other organs in the present study. Cadmium is generally more concentrated in kidney than liver. In terms of absolute amount, the cadmium content of liver would be much higher.

It is generally agreed that cadmium has a long biological half-life and as a result, tends to accumulate in the kidney and liver of mammals. Denton *et al.*² showed a positive correlation between cadmium and age of dugong in both kidney and liver.

The level of iron in the heart is amongst the lowest (Table 2). The level of zinc is also lower than kidney but of similar concentration with the spleen (Table 2). A detectable quantity of aluminum is present in the heart. Other metals detected in the present study are manganese, copper, nickel and lead. Cadmium and cobalt were not detected (Table 2).

Phosphorus and sulfur in liver, kidney, spleen and heart :

Phosphorus and sulfur are the two non-metals analyzed in the organs of dugong. The level of phosphorus and sulfur are consistently high in all the samples of dugong (Table 3). Phosphorus in liver and spleen ranges between 9184 and $11268 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ (dry wt.). The concentration of phosphorus in kidney ($7694 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.) is lower than the concentration in liver and spleen while that in the heart is the lowest of all the organs of dugong ($4452 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.).

Phosphorus occurs in mammalian soft tissues where it is essential for anabolic and catabolic reactions due to its

Table 3. Phosphorus and sulfur ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt) in dugong organs (mean values)

Sample	Phosphorus	Sulfur
QNL (liver)	11268	8958
SB1 (liver)	11077	9445
SB2 (liver)	9184	8127
SB (liver)	10677	11070
SB (spleen)	9495	7604
SB (heart)	4452	6221
SB (kidney)	7694	9283

role in formation of high-energy bonds (ATP, ADP). Phosphorus is also a precursor for phospholipids that are important in the formation of cell membranes and in cellular permeability. Phosphorus is also a precursor for the biosynthesis of DNA and a contributor to the buffering capacity of body fluids of cells. The concentrations of sulfur are also high in all the samples. The concentrations ranges between ($6221\text{--}10677 \mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ dry wt.). Sulfur is a component of protein. It is found in two of the commonly found amino acids (cysteine and methionine). Sulfur is involved in the formation of sulfur-bonds that stabilize the protein secondary and tertiary structures. Both the elements occur widely in nature and may contribute to the high concentrations of phosphorus and sulfur in the tissues of dugong. Phosphorus and sulfur are also involved in the biological functions of the tissues.

Conclusion :

The elemental analysis on the dugong tissue reveals an extremely high level of iron in the liver, which is consistent with the elevated concentration of iron in the diet of dugong. High level of aluminum is also associated with high level this element in the diet. Dugong kidney has shown to accumulate high level of cadmium. Levels of other metals in the tissue do not reflect anthropogenic activities. Histological study failed to support the deleterious effect of high iron in the tissue⁴.

The analysis indicates that the high iron without damaging the tissue may be natural to this species of sea mammals. The dugong may have acquired an ability to stand the severe level of iron in the seagrass that is its main diet. The high levels of iron are consistent with the extreme deposits seen on Perl's staning. Unlike human pathological condition of thalassemia, where high iron is associated with liver tissue damage, the dugong liver can maintain normal liver cellular histology in the presence of extremely high iron levels. This suggests that the dugong may well employ unusual and interesting strategies for preventing tissue damage under these high iron conditions.

Experimental

Source of sample : A young female dugong (SB) was found dead in Shark Bay (24–26° S, 113° E) Western Australia, Australia, and was brought to Veterinary School of Murdoch University, Western Australia, Australia, for post-mortem study. Some organs, such as liver, heart, kidney and spleen were available for the present study. The organs were immediately removed from the body and frozen at –20° until required for analysis.

Three more livers were also obtained but this time they were obtained from different dugongs, two from Shark Bay (SB1 and SB2) (24–26° S, 113° E) Western Australia, Australia, and one from Northern Territory (QNL), approximately 1 km E.S.E. of Dugong Creek (UTM coordinates 683800 E and 8246800 N).

Analysis of tissue samples : Samples were taken from various regions (that is from the edges and inside) of each organ for acid digestion. The sample was washed with deionized water to remove excess blood and fat. It was weighed after the excess water was drawn away with filter paper and kept in an acid-washed polyethylene container. It was then freeze-dried at –50° and held in vacuum for 72 h before digestion. Digestion was carried out in triplicate. A control from human liver was included. The clear solution of the acid-digest of dugong organ was analyzed for elemental composition by ICP-AES.

Digestion of tissue with acid : Samples were prepared for analysis of the elements by digestion with concentrated nitric acid and perchloric acid. Before digestion, the freeze-dried tissue was ground into powder form and stored in a polyethylene container that was kept in a glass dessicator under vacuum until analysis. Each sample powder was weighed accurately to give approximately 100 mg into a 100 ml acid-washed conical flask for acid digestion. A blank [concentrated nitric acid, 5 ml and perchloric acid (35% v/v), 1.0 ml] and a control (human liver tissue commercially prepared) were also included. Concentrated nitric acid (5 ml) was added to the powder and heated at 70° until all

organic materials were dissolved and a clear solution was formed. The temperature was increased to 165°. Perchloric acid (35%, v/v; 1.0 ml) was added to the clear solution and heating was continued until a white fume of perchloric acid (after ~ 1 h) evolved. Distilled water then was added to it and cooled to room temperature. The solution was made up to the mark with distilled water and filtered to remove any undissolved silica particles. The sample was then analyzed for Fe, Zn, Cu, Pb, Mn, Cd, Ni, Co, Al, P and S by ICP-AES (inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer, Varian Liberty 200 at Environmental Science, School of Biological and Environmental Science, Murdoch University).

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